
WORKSHOP REPORT

EXPLORING KEY ASPECTS OF NOVEL AND FUNCTIONAL SEAFOOD AND AQUACULTURE PRODUCTS

Thank you for having joined us for our workshop on the exploration of aspects of Novel and Functional Foods that are important for seafood and aquaculture products. We appreciated your active participation and valuable insights.

DATE AND TIME

May 14, 2025
1:30 PM - 3:00 PM

LOCATION

Seminar Room 2.44
O'Rahilly Building (ORB)
College RD, University College Cork

WHO ATTENDED

Professionals from the seafood and aquaculture sector
Researchers and scientists interested in food innovation
Entrepreneurs and business owners in the seafood industry

This project has received funding from the European Union under Grand Agreement N° 101084180

ABOUT THE WORKSHOP

Our main objective was to increase the general knowledge about **novel and functional foods** and collect ideas for **successful and competitive products related to seafood and aquaculture**. The main part was to identify content for upcoming webinars to fill existing knowledge gaps. The workshop was part of the NOVAFOODIES project. The workshop was conducted in two separate groups. This report presents the combined output of both groups.

ABOUT THE NOVAFOODIES PROJECT

NOVAFOODIES is an innovative project aimed at developing new functional products derived from **marine and freshwater sources, utilizing more sustainable production methods** while maintaining sectoral competitiveness. The project will also focus on enhancing consumer trust through research on **product traceability and monitoring the environmental impact** of production processes.

AGENDA

- 1.) WARM UP
- 2.) INTRODUCTION
- 3.) BRAINWALKING
- 4.) PRIORITISATION
- 5.) CLOSING

OBJECTIVES

- 1.) RAISE GENERAL KNOWLEDGE
- 2.) COLLECT IDEAS
- 3.) IDENTIFY KNOWLEDGE GAPS

NON-OBJECTIVES

- 1.) CLASSROOM LECTURE
- 2.) DELIVERING ENTIRELY NEW CONTENT

FOODS OR FOOD INGREDIENTS THAT HAVE NOT BEEN WIDELY CONSUMED BY PEOPLE BEFORE MAY 1997.

- NEW FOODS
- FOODS FROM NEW SOURCES
- NEW SUBSTANCES USED AS FOOD INGREDIENTS
- NEW WAYS OF PRODUCING FOODS

MAIN TOPICS YOU DISCUSSED

What are important aspects for seafood and aquaculture products to be successfully placed and competitive on the market?

What are important aspects for strong consumer acceptance of seafood and aquaculture products?

What are the main challenges in the Novel Food application process and what would help you dealing with them?

What are the main challenges in the declaration of health claims and what will help you dealing with them?

What are safety and security considerations of seafood and aquaculture products? (considering human health, environmental, social, economic aspects)

METHODOLOGY

2 GROUPS

BRAINWALKING

CLUSTERING

PRESENTATION

PRIORITISATION

SUMMARY OF YOUR INPUT

STRONG CONSUMER ACCEPTANCE

- Sensory appeal (taste, smell, texture, appearance, similarity to known products)
- Price and value (affordability)
- Health and safety (health benefits, nutritional value, allergens, functionality)
- Ethical and environmental considerations (animal welfare, etc.)
- Trust (familiarity, transparency, clear labeling, etc)
- Marketing and communication
- Innovation and novelty

SAFETY AND SECURITY

- Human health and food safety (non-toxic, allergenes, GMO, cross-contamination)
- Environmental safety and sustainability (pollution, waste, carbon footprint, resource depletion, habitat loss, alien species, LCA and end-of-life, low energy and production cost)
- Social and ethical considerations (worker welfare, fairness, employee opportunities, food sovereignty, community or industry displacement)
- Economic and systemic resilience (low costs, local supply, import dependency)

MARKET SUCCESS AND COMPETITIVENESS

- Product quality and appeal (labelling, naming, convenience, nutritious, organic, ecological, sensory aspects)
- Market fit and consumer relevance (target group, trends, consumer trust, acceptance, social media, addressing real needs)
- Innovation and differentiation (diversification, competitive advantage, efficiency through modern technology)
- Cost and profitability (price parity with equivalents, yield, production cost vs. profit, personnel costs, etc.)
- Production and supply chain (scale, stability against seasonal conditions, good quality ingredients, availability, location and functionality)
- Distribution and market access (also international markets)
- Brand and image (e.g. social media visibility)

SUMMARY OF YOUR INPUT

CHALLENGES NOVEL FOODS

- Regulatory and legal challenges (compliance with EU regulations, i.e. Novel Food regulation, sanitary certification, proven safety and quality, proprietary rights)
- Time and cost barriers (time consuming, expensive and complicated process, low funds, profitability only for larger companies/associations)
- Scientific and technical requirements (safe for consumption, improved nutritional profile, market equivalent, history of consumption)
- Consumer and market acceptance (cultural aspects, availability, novelty, local production, community, engagement)
- Communication and visibility (promotion, transparency, political narrative)
- Support structures and collaboration

CHALLENGES HEALTH CLAIMS

- Scientific evidence and validation (clinical research and experimental analyses, long-term studies and data collection, large studies, proper meta-analyses)
- Regulatory and legal barriers (legislation, need to be registered by authorities, FDA/MDA approval, historical consumption)
- Technical and product-specific challenges (availability of bioactive compound during shelf-life, addition of nutritious elements, formulation of claims)
- Research design and resources
- Communication and public perception
- Bureaucratic and institutional hurdles

Association
& others

University

Industry

PRIORITIES OF DIFFERENT ACTORS

PARTICIPANTS

31

NO. PARTICIPANTS

11

UNIVERSITY MEMBERS

6

INDUSTRY MEMBERS

13

ASSOCIATIONS
& OTHERS

University

For participants accounting to this group, **price and affordability** were identified as key factors for consumer acceptance and ranked among the top priorities. **Sustainability** was emphasized as a critical safety consideration alongside the importance of **product selection and quality assurance when stating health claims**.

Industry

For participants from this group, no single aspect stood out as a top priority. Their focus was **spread across several key areas**: sustainability as safety consideration, challenges posed by Novel Food legislation - particularly for smaller companies - and the importance of product selection and quality assurance in substantiating health claims among them.

Associations & others

Participants belonging to this group prioritised **price and affordability** to be important for consumer acceptance as one of the key aspects for them. Additionally, **sustainability** in relation to safety and security and **identifying market needs and trends** for successful market placement of a product were chosen as most relevant.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

Participants expressed strong consumer acceptance, with **price and affordability** emerging as the most influential factor. **Environmental friendliness** also plays a significant role, along with notable consumer interest in **clean labeling and nutritional value**.

Sustainability and environmental impact - like LCAs and end-of-life considerations - were key safety and security concerns among participants. **Low energy costs** were also seen as important, alongside **broader social considerations** like employment, industry impact and public health.

Participants highlighted **cost and pricing** as key challenges for successful market entry. The alignment with **current trends and effective marketing strategies** was also seen as essential, along with the need for a **reliable and robust supply chain** to support long-term success.

Ensuring and **proving food safety** was identified as the most critical challenge when it comes to Novel Foods. Participants also highlighted the **high costs** of such procedures as a barrier for small companies, along with **complex and time-consuming legislative requirements**.

Ensuring **consistent product quality and selection** was seen as a foundational issue when stating health claims. **Scientific validation** - often requiring costly studies and testing - was another major hurdle along with the challenge of **consumer trust** in health claims themselves.

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